

Dehumanization of Human Beings Due to Two World Wars: A Historical Perspective

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Dehumanization, World War, Conflict, League, Nations, Ineffectiveness, Dictatorship, Alliances, Nationalism, Military.

Received : 25.03.2025

Revised : 27.05.2025

Accepted: 20.06.2025

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ABSTRACT

This article exposes the period of the First and Second World War. The paper presents the dehumanization policies of human beings due to two world wars in a historical perspective. If we analyse the period from the end of the WWI to WWII, we will be able to understand that The World War II was the final phase of the World War I. In these period there are many crisis in the world and great depression which were the symbol of dehumanization activities. They were the largest military conflicts in human history. Both wars involved military alliances between different groups of countries. The world warring nations were divided into two groups namely 'The Central Powers' and 'The Allied Powers'. Within the two wars the First World war was especially heinous because of the genocide of Jewish people perpetrated by the Nazis. Between the two wars the World War II was the largest conflict in human history and devastated Europe, Asia, North Africa, and large portions of the Pacific. The two conflicts merged into a single global struggle during which a coalition of Allied powers defeated a coalition of Axis states. This text uses a largely narrative approach, interspersed with a separate section on economic, psychological, and demographic aspects of the conflict to describe the origins, course, and consequences of the war. Beside it will reveal the terrible incidents which were responsible for dehumanization policy of human being due to two world wars.

INTRODUCTION

The First World War (1914-18) is a significant event in the history of the 20th century. It was at this time that the world witnessed an all-out war. Its prevalence spread everywhere. History shows that from 1790 to 1913, twice as many people died in the First World War as the number of people killed in them from the effects of dehumanization policy. Later, the war ended with various treaties and organizations. But in fact, we find that even after the end of the First World War, the trend of world peace did not continue. Expecting a war like the Napoleonic campaigns of the previous century, politicians and military commanders failed to predict the destructive power of twentieth century technology (Varin, 2014, P. 1). From the first world war until the second world war, many negative, embarrassing and dehumanizing events were born in the world. After the World War I, the League of Nations, formed for peace, failed in its peace-building efforts. As a result, the World War II finally broke out in 1939. So it can be said that the period from 1919 to 1939 was a long armistice. After this long ceasefire, the world once again faced a terrible war. So it can be undoubtedly said that although the timing of these two wars is different, the second was initiated dehumanized influence of the first.

OBJECTIVES

This research aims to investigate how the political, economic, social, and military factors of early 20th century Europe laid the groundwork for systemic dehumanization of individuals and entire communities during both wars. It examines how nationalism, militarism, alliances, and imperial rivalries triggered conflicts and led to viewing humans as expendable means to achieve state objectives. A key objective is to examine how trench warfare, chemical weapons, mass propaganda, and technological innovations in warfare stripped soldiers and civilians of their individuality and human dignity, making mass violence acceptable and even routinized. The study looks into post-war treaties like the Treaty of Versailles, the failure of peacekeeping institutions such as the League of Nations, and international power struggles (e.g., the Washington Naval Conference) to demonstrate how unresolved tensions and punitive measures perpetuated cycles of hatred and dehumanization, paving the road to World War II. The research seeks to integrate insights from historians (Keegan, Overy), philosophers (Arendt, Bauman), psychologists (Milgram), and literary works (Remarque, Orwell, Levi) to provide a multidisciplinary understanding of how people and governments rationalized atrocities by denying the humanity of others. Finally, the research aims to demonstrate that the legacy of these dehumanizing mechanisms did not end with 1945; instead, they influence current global politics, armed conflicts, and human rights debates. By tracing their historical trajectory, the research intends to contribute to discussions on preventing

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What role did propaganda play in the dehumanization of enemy populations during the two World Wars?
2. How did dehumanization affect troops' and civilians' psychological well-being during and after the wars?
3. How did views of human worth and dignity change as a result of military technology advancements?
4. How did racial ideologies contribute to continuation of dehumanization during the two World Wars?
5. What effects did dehumanization have on efforts at post-war reconciliation and international relations?
6. How much did depictions of dehumanization throughout the conflicts appear in literature, art and the media?
7. In what ways did persecution and genocide, like the Holocaust, raise awareness of human rights and dignity around the world?

LITERATURE REVIEW

The two World Wars of the 20th century led to unprecedented destruction, reshaping societies, economies, and human perceptions of morality and dignity. Scholars from various disciplines, including history, sociology, philosophy, and literature, have explored how these wars dehumanized individuals and entire populations. This literature review examines key works on the dehumanization of human beings during and after World War I and World War II, focusing on historical accounts, psychological studies, and literary representations. Dehumanization in war has been widely studied in the fields of history, psychology, and philosophy. Scholars like David Livingstone Smith (2011) in *Less Than Human: Why We Demean, Enslave, and Exterminate Others* argue that dehumanization is a psychological process used to justify mass violence. Hannah Arendt (1951) in *The Origins of Totalitarianism* discusses how totalitarian regimes dehumanized individuals by stripping them of their individuality and reducing them to expendable entities. Additionally, Jonathan Glover (1999) in *Humanity: A Moral History of the Twentieth Century* examines the mechanisms through which people commit atrocities by seeing others as less than human. These works provide a theoretical framework for understanding how the two World Wars systematically dehumanized millions of people. The trench warfare and use of poison gas exemplified the erosion of human dignity. Paul Fussell (1975) in *The Great War and Modern Memory* explores how the war transformed perceptions of humanity and desensitized soldiers and civilians alike. Erich Maria Remarque's novel *All Quiet on the Western Front* (1929) offers a literary depiction of the psychological impact of war on soldiers, showing how individuals became mere instruments of violence. Historians such as Stéphane Audoin-Rouzeau and Annette Becker (2000) in *14-18: Understanding the Great*

War emphasize how wartime propaganda dehumanized the enemy, making killing more psychologically acceptable. World War II escalated the brutality of war with totalitarian regimes, genocidal policies, and large-scale civilian bombings. The Holocaust, as documented by Raul Hilberg (1961) in *The Destruction of the European Jews*, was one of the most extreme manifestations of dehumanization, where entire populations were systematically reduced to numbers and exterminated. George Orwell's *1984* (1949) and Primo Levi's *If This Is a Man* (1947) offer literary insights into the erasure of individuality under oppressive regimes. Additionally, Richard Overy (1995) in *Why the Allies Won* highlights how dehumanization was not limited to the Axis powers, as strategic bombings by the Allies also involved justifying civilian casualties. Psychological studies, such as Stanley Milgram's (1974) *Obedience to Authority*, suggest that the bureaucratic structure of war facilitated moral disengagement, making atrocities easier to commit. The long-term psychological effects of war have been widely studied. John Keegan (1993) in *A History of Warfare* argues that the mechanization of war in the 20th century alienated soldiers from the act of killing, further dehumanizing both the victims and the perpetrators. The Nuremberg Trials and subsequent human rights developments, as analyzed by Philippe Sands (2016) in *East West Street*, reveal how post-war efforts attempted to restore human dignity. However, as explored by Zygmunt Bauman (1989) in *Modernity and the Holocaust*, bureaucratic efficiency remains a dangerous mechanism for dehumanization in modern societies.

METHODOLOGY

In order to investigate the issue of dehumanization during the First and Second World Wars, this study uses a qualitative historical research design. The research aims to comprehend how war policies, beliefs, and experiences eroded human dignity and identity across many populations by examining secondary historical sources. Information will be gathered from secondary sources including academic publications, peer-reviewed studies, propaganda posters, and images. Purposively chosen sources will be chosen based on their relevance to the themes of dehumanization, their representation of various social and geographic groups such as soldiers, civilians, Jews, and colonial subjects. Their coverage of both World Wars and the main participating countries such as the United States, Japan, Germany, Britain, and the Soviet Union.

The materials will be analyzed for recurrent themes, including dehumanization of races and ethnic groups, psychological trauma and moral harm, propaganda and enemy stereotyping, violations of human rights, and acts of genocidal violence. To guarantee depth and nuance, interpretations will be guided by critical theory, including post-colonial and psychological frameworks as well as historical context. Although there are no human participants in this study, ethical consideration will be given to the tactful handling of delicate and graphic historical material. Every group shall be fairly represented and presentist prejudice will be avoided. The interpretive nature of qualitative historical analysis, possible bias in propaganda materials from the conflict, and the

availability of English-language sources could all be barriers to the study. Triangulating several sources, however, will improve objectivity and dependability. This research intends to follow APA 7th citation manual for references.

RESEARCH GAP

While extensive research exists on the occurrence of dehumanization during both World Wars, there is insufficient integrated study of how the cultural, psychological, and moral breakdown caused by World War I directly conditioned societies to accept, reproduce, and escalate dehumanizing policies in World War II. This gap suggests the need for a comparative, interdisciplinary analysis of continuity in dehumanizing attitudes, technologies, and institutional behaviors across the two conflicts. The literature mentions that dehumanization occurred and was terrible, but does not fully explain how the psychological normalization of dehumanization in WWI influenced societies, leaders, and soldiers to commit or tolerate even greater atrocities in WWII. Many studies isolate either WWI or WWII dehumanization, but few examine continuity, escalation, or transmission of learned attitudes across the interwar period. There is little critical synthesis combining military history, cultural history, psychology, and moral philosophy to show how the horrors of WWI normalized large-scale moral disengagement, paving the way for WWII's atrocities.

DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS

The Primary Stage of Dehumanization During The Wars: The Beginning of The World War I And Its Dynamics:

The First World War began in 1914 and ended in 1918. We have to think that The First World War started at a time when there was widespread industrialization in Europe. At the same time, the ultra-nationalist movement was born. These events gave rise to The First World War. Like a centre of gravity the war deforms the human life as well as the human body (Martini, 2012, P. 2). The First World War began on June 28, 1914, when Archduke Ferdinand, Prince of Austria, was killed by an assailant in Sarajevo, the capital of Bosnia. Serbia's hostilities to Austria had previously escalated. Serbian leaders were believed to be involved in the killings. Austria issued an extreme letter with certain conditions in protest against the killing. But when Serbia did not comply with those conditions, the Austrian and German armies raided Sarajevo. Russia and France stood by Serbia. As a result, Germany invaded France and Russia. And that's how the war started. It was through the war that the Central Powers Alliance and the Allied Alliance were born.

It should be noted here that the first Bolshevik Revolution took place in Russia in 1917, and in 1917, the United States took part in the war on behalf of the Allies. In doing so, the United States abandoned the concept of the "Monroe Doctrine" (non-interference in European affairs). During the war, Russia withdrew from the war by signing the 'Brest Litovsk' treaty with Germany and annexed the

western provinces of Russian-occupied Germany. Russia had no choice but to make this treaty. On the other hand, when some American ships were destroyed by German torpedoes, the United States had to go to war. The Allied alliance began to enjoy one success after another. It is worth mentioning here that undoubtedly Germany's ambitions triggered this world war, but at the same time it is also true that there was a conflict of interest between many states at that time. Before the outbreak of World War I, Europe was divided into two military camps. On the one hand there was the Three-Power Alliance (Germany, Austria, and Italy), on the other was the Two-Power Alliance (Russia and France) which in turn became the Triple Alliance (England, France, and Russia). This triple alliance was dangerous for Germany. This alliance between the states was also reflected in WWI.

Although WWI was by no means the most violent of wars, the rate of death, the needless suffering, the flagrant disregard for the laws of war, and the seeming futility of it all make the Great War arguably the most inhumane and wasteful conflict in history. The First World War of 1914-1918 was marked by trenches, poison gas, and the new and terrible diseases. Over just four years, European states engaged in a total war that killed over nine million soldiers and seven million civilians of all origins (Varin, 2014, P. 1).

The trenches in World War One were likened to "*hell on earth*" (Varin, 2014, P. 2). These trenches, which spanned more than 765 kilometers from the Belgian coast to the Swiss border, resulted in conditions for the soldiers that can only be described as cruel- frigid temperatures, persistent exposure to illness and rodents, and the fear of flamethrowers and poison gas. Soldiers faced the unpredictability of a lingering death from poison gas in addition to the horrible conditions of the trenches. Despite the comparatively low fatality rate, almost 1.2 million troops were affected by poison gas during World War One, the first combat to utilize chemical weapons in such a systematic and experimental way.

Some Notable Issues of Dehumanization Behind the First World War

Extreme-nationalism:

The practice of dehumanization was continued through extreme nationalism within several powers. One of the reasons for the WWI was that in Italy and Germany, extreme-nationalism instilled an unprecedented power in politics. It was a part of dehumanization behind the First World War. It was this ultra-nationalism that prompted European powers in Asia, Africa, and the Balkans to wage a fierce struggle for statehood. Created a sense of pride, rivalry, and competition among the European countries, particularly in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. Germany, Austria-Hungary, Britain, France, and Russia were among the European powers vying for supremacy and reputation. This is how Balkan nationalism emerged against the Turkish Sultanate. The inevitable outcome of these situations was World War I. In multinational empires where different ethnic groups wanted independence or autonomy based on nationalist ambitions, nationalism increased tensions and served as a symbol of dehumanization.

Balkan Crisis and Dehumanization of European powers:

In 1912-14, European powers focused on the Balkans. At this time, the Balkans became a centre of ethnic conflict, nationalist movements, and competition from the great powers. The reform movement of the neo-Turks inside Turkey and Turkey's failure to maintain control over the Balkans made the immediate collapse of the Ottoman Empire evident. Most European powers continued to calculate their respective gains and losses in the possible collapse of the Ottoman Empire. In 1912, Serbia formed the "Balkan League" with the aim of ending Ottoman rule in the Balkans. During the year, Balkan League members Serbia, Bulgaria, Greece and Montenegro declared war against Turkey. Turkey was defeated in this war, known as the 'First Balkan War', and the remaining European territory except Albania was lost to Turkey. But failing to gain the territory it hoped for, Bulgaria invaded Serbia in 1913, known as the 'Second Balkan War'. After the Second Balkan War, Serbia emerged as a powerful regional power, threatening Bosnia-Herzegovina under the Austro-Hungarian Empire. As a result, Austria became more dependent on Germany to protect its interests.

Economic Competition:

In the late 19th and first half of the 20th century, the main features of world history were industrial and trade struggles and attempts to build colonial empires. Economic competition led to a conflict between Britain and Germany. This was one of the reasons for dehumanization policy behind WWI. Dehumanization resulted from the competition between European nations for colonies and markets worldwide. As developed countries fought for markets and resources to support their economies. Due to economic causes like the need for weapons and equipment production, European powers significantly increased their military capacities. This arms race increased tensions and put a burden on national budgets.

Conflicting Alliances:

The remarkable reasons for dehumanization are the extreme militarism and conflicting military alliances of different European states. At its core was Bismarck's anti-French sentiment. Bismarck (father of modern Germany) was peaceful minded. Nothing was further from Bismarck's mind than disarmament, which he called a "confused humanitarian idea". Quite different ideas were maturing in his head, as the world was to learn only a few months later (Eyck, 1950, P. 163). But he realized that the defeat of the Franco-Prussian War could never be forgotten in France, and so Bismarck launched a military alliance to protect Germany from future invasions of France. As a result, the whole of Europe was divided into two conflicting military forces. On the one hand, the three-power alliance (Germany, Austria and Italy), on the other hand, the three-power alliance (France, Russia and England). The two powers faced each other during various international crises between 1906 and 1914. On the diplomatic front with Morocco, Germany was humiliated by Britain and France, and Germany and its allies Austria and Italy were not forgotten.

Military Competition:

Military competition was the common cause of the World War I. This competition was responsible for dehumanization during the war. In 1913, Germany's troops stood at 870,000. In response, the mandatory military service in France was increased to three years. Russia also mandates military training. Britain also increased its naval power. This is why this era is called "The Age of Armed Peace". The world's biggest and strongest navy was the British Royal Navy. Germany greatly increased its fleet in an effort to challenge British dominance. In 1906, Britain debuted the ground-breaking HMS Dreadnought, a battleship that was more powerful, quicker, more heavily armed than its predecessors. In response, Germany produced its own dreadnoughts, which fueled the arms race even further. Germany possessed 17 dreadnoughts by 1914, while Britain had 29. Germany increased the size of its army to more than 4 million men. With over 6 million troops, Russia had the biggest potential force, although being slowest to deploy. Britain retaliated with naval blockades after Germany invented submarine warfare, endangering British supply routes. Machine guns, artillery (Big Bertha), poison gas, tanks, aircraft, and submarines (U-boats) were among the new weaponry created. It was as if human being was engaged in an arms race to kill human being.

Different Effects of Dehumanization During Ceasefire And Path To The Second World War

The First World War and the Second World War were two different wars, but in reality World War II was a final stage of World War I. After WWI, in the midst of a long truce, various events of dehumanization arose in the world which were the determinants of The Second World War. This led to World War II. The following events of dehumanization that took place after World War I until the time of World War II (1939):

Reaction of the Treaty of Versailles of 1919 (Peace Keeping Policy But Resulted Dehumanization):

In early May 1919, after working tirelessly for several months the Big Four (David Lloyd George of Britain, Georges Clemenceau of France, Woodrow Wilson of the United States, and Vittorio Orlando of Italy) were able to finalize the provisions of the treaty with Germany. On May 6, a plenary assembly accepted the accord summary. The German delegation was permitted to join the conference on May 7 and gave them a presentation of the 80,000-word original agreement. On June 28, Germany signed the treaty at the Palace of Versailles' Hall of Mirrors indicating its acceptance of its terms. This agreement is known in history as "The Treaty of Versailles".

The Treaty of Versailles in 1919 was planned to suppress the defeated powers of WWI. Later it made all states more dangerous than ever. Britain, France, Germany, Turkey, who won the First World War, were imposed on them so that they could never stand up again. As a result, extreme-nationalism was born in Germany. In the post-World War I period, there was a massive arms race all over the world which practicalized dehumanization. After WWI aggressive imperialism was observed all over the world. Japan's occupation of Manchuria

in 1931, Italy's occupation of Ethiopia in 1937, the Spanish Civil War, etc. complicated the international situation at that time. The German nation, which was devastated by the First World War couldn't forget its defeat. Mussolini's installation of a fascist regime in Italy sparked a conflict-like environment. All things considered; the world is experiencing instability. Consequently, World War II broke out.

Founding of the League of Nations (Road to peace but failed):

The world was profoundly startled by the First World War in 1914. This was a significant moment in human history. The entire world gasped at its size and devastation. Under such circumstances, contemplative individuals begin to consider ways to prevent war and establish lasting international peace. In actuality, it is evident that conflicts may be resolved at any moment and between states; peaceful methods were also taken into consideration in place of utilizing force. This way of thinking was strengthened by the destruction caused by World War I. In 1917, Pope Benedict XVI urged that international conflicts be settled via dialogue and compromise rather than going to war once more. President Woodrow Wilson of the United States unveiled his 14-point plan for post-World War I peace in Europe on April 2, 1917. It was introduced at the Fourteenth Point Policy's Article 14- "An international body must be formed to protect the independence and security of all states, large and small. "

The Failure and Dissolution of The League of Nations:

Similar to how the establishment of the League of Nations that brought about world peace during WWI gave people optimism at the time. The organization's failure and eventual demise within a few years sent the world into a state of despair. The League of Nations was unable to meet the expectations for which it was established. Many aggressive situation influence on dehumanization. As a result, the League of Nations became ineffective and automatically went extinct. One of the reasons for this can be attributed to the absence of major powers. The League of Nations was also pushed by England and France, who frequently had to keep their minds open for others to follow. For example, when Hitler came to power in Germany it was again equipped with new weapons. But the league had not taken any effective action against it. Moreover, the league's operations and constitution had numerous problems. The League's General Assembly had very little authority. The former Soviet Union referred to the league as "*the club of capitalist countries*" due to its wide range of activities. The League of Nations eventually collapsed for a number of reasons.

The Italo-Abyssinian War and the Spanish Civil War were responsible for dehumanization which led the failure of the League of Nations. As we will soon see, this was not the case when Italy decided to take military action against Ethiopia and when the Spanish Civil War broke out. We could observe how the future Axis and Allied alignments were beginning to stabilize throughout the Spanish War. European States were picking their side without knowing that a major armed conflict would arise in the end and that it would affect almost every corner of the world (Matsushima, 2022, P. 99). Both conflicts clearly reflected the inherent flaws in the League of Nations' decision-making process and its inability

to adequately implement peaceful solutions. In flagrant defiance of international law and all other international standards, Benito Mussolini and his fascist government invaded Ethiopia in October 3, 1935. The Second Italo-Abyssinian War quickly broke out once Italy mobilized its army. The two nations' antagonistic relationship began with the Treaty of Ucciale and continued through the First Italo-Ethiopian War, which saw African nations defeat European nations before the Treaty of Addis Ababa was signed in 1896, thereby ending the war. Italy was forced to acknowledge Ethiopia's independence from colonial authority following the conclusion of the war. But soon after, Italy's expansionist plans in Africa were renewed.

Washington Naval Conference in 1921-22 (U.S. influence on Japan):

After WWI Japan was full of naval power. It was viewed by the US as a danger to him. In an effort to weaken Japan's naval might in East Asia, U.S. President Harding called a conference in Washington on November 12, 1921. The meeting ended on February 2, 1922. At the suggestion of the United States, a meeting was held in Washington in 1921 to address the issues facing the Pacific and Far East. The summit was attended by nine nations- the United States, Britain, France, Italy, Portugal, Belgium, Japan, Holland, and China. During the conference, seven agreements were inked. The "Washington Naval Treaty" or "Five Powers Agreement" was one of the most famous of these agreements, which was negotiated to lessen naval competition and naval strength in the Far East.

On February 6, 1922, the "Washington Naval Treaty" on the mitigation of Naval Power in the Far East was signed between the United States, Britain, France, Japan, and Italy. In 1919-1921, Japan was chafing under a postwar recession. It was Navy Minister Kato Tomosaburo-the architect of the "eight-eight fleet" plan who was the first to recognize that this program was destined to be only a paper plan (Asada, 1993, P. 86). According to the traditional understanding, which the current author previously contributed to Kato's ideas on naval limitation and national security were passed down through these "*heirs*" as naval orthodoxy into the 1920s and the early 1930s. The three fundamental tenets of the Imperial Japanese Navy which had been in place since 1907, "a seventy-percent ratio", the "eight-eight fleet," and the idea that the United States was the "hypothetical enemy" were after all abandoned by Kato Tomosaburo himself. Rather, Kato Kanji and his allies in the fleets and Naval General Staff would finally take over the Japanese naval system by rejecting the Washington Treaty.

Kato Tomosaburo was appointed prime minister in June 1922 and concurrently served as navy minister for over a year. Implementing the Washington treaties was his immediate responsibility, but more challenging issues included the modification of the Imperial National Defense Policy to follow the new direction he had established in Washington and the institutional reforms pertaining to civilian navy ministers. Naval men were even more unhappy with the drastic personnel cutbacks brought on by naval reductions than with the demolition of ships that were already completed or were in the process of being built. Even more shocking was the drastic reduction in Naval Academy enrollment, which

saw less than 5% of the preceding class enroll in the incoming class of 1922. The gloomy repercussions were dire. It was no accident that three of the young officers who would later be implicated in the "May 15 [assassination] Incident" of 1932 were from the classes most impacted by this impact. Since Kato Tomosaburo's reform plan only pushed the Naval General Staff to take preventative action, it ultimately failed.

Treaty of Locarno of 1925 (Reaction of France and Germany):

Fearing one other's wrath, France and Germany attempted to sign a friendship treaty after the Geneva Protocol failed in 1924. In this case, France reacted when German Foreign Minister Strassmann suggested an arrangement. France wanted Poland, Belgium, Czechoslovakia, and Italy to take part in the friendship negotiations, even if Germany accepted the treaty proposal. Representatives of Poland, Belgium, Czechoslovakia, Britain, Italy, France and Germany met in Locarno, the capital of Switzerland (October 1925), in a friendly atmosphere in which seven treaties were signed in Locarno. All seven treaties are collectively known in history as the Treaty of Locarno. The Rhineland security pact between Germany, Great Britain, France, Belgium, and Italy is the most significant of the accords. Except for the French and Belgian treaties' omission of Article 21 of the treaties with Poland and Czechoslovakia, the terms of the four arbitration treaties are identical. Additionally, France concluded two security treaties with Poland and Czechoslovakia, respectively, which provide for mutual assistance in the event that Germany resorts to unprovoked armed action and similar assistance in the event that either country is attacked without provocation and the League Council is unable to stop it. It is specifically stated that conflicts that began before the treaty's conclusion and belonging to the past, or issues for which previous treaties have made a settlement provision, are not covered by the arbitration that is being considered. However, a number of problems hampered its usefulness. It was unable to stop the rise of the Nazis. Hitler's ascent to power and subsequent breach of the treaty- the remilitarization of the Rhineland in 1936 were not stopped by it. Its scope is similarly constrained. It largely focused on western borders, although tensions persisted elsewhere, particularly in Eastern Europe. The treaty failed to address fundamental political and economic issues, which ultimately led to the outbreak of World War II.

Ineffectiveness of Kellogg-Briand Pact (1928):

France once again became concerned about preserving world peace and security as the spirit of trust that the Locarno Treaty's harmony fostered among European nations waned for a number of reasons. Nations were more concerned about their security. "France is full of the idea that she is going to control, overwhelm and keep under Germany. It is only France who could give us trouble now", Lloyd George told his Cabinet on 30 June 1920 (Adamthwaite, 2021, P. 3). Consequently, A ceasefire agreement was reached in Paris on August 29, 1928, by representatives of fifteen different countries. This agreement is known as the Kellogg-Briand Agreement or the Paris Agreement. By 1930, the treaty had 62 states, for a total of 65. The Kellogg-Briand Pact was signed in 1928 with the goal of outlawing the use of war as a national policy instrument. However, it didn't

work very well. Due to its impracticality, dehumanizing activities have spread throughout the world. Despite its noble intentions, it failed to halt the aggressiveness that led to the Second World War.

The treaty was supplemented with a set of arbitration treaties (Arbitration and Conciliation Treaties) and with defensive alliance treaties between France and Czechoslovakia and France and Poland (Lesaffer, 2011, P. 2). It failed for many notable causes such as Lack of Enforcement Mechanisms, Ambiguous Language, Rise of Militarism and Expansionism, No Link to the League of Nations, U.S. Isolationism. There would be no actual repercussions for nations who violated the accord. Although war was prohibited under the treaty, it did not specify what "War" or "Aggression" meant. Using "Self-defense" or other pretexts, nations could defend their armed operations. In addition to being independent, the League of Nations lacked the actual authority to prevent aggression. Without the backing of a strong international institution, the agreement remained merely symbolic. The United States, one of the signatories, upheld its isolationist posture and shunned military commitments. This reluctance hampered international efforts to impose peace. An idealistic endeavor to avert war, the Kellogg-Briand Pact failed because it was not upheld, its terms were unclear, and radical nationalist sentiments began to surface. Ultimately, it failed to stop the outbreak of World War II in 1939.

London Naval Conference of 1930 (Reducing Naval Supremacy):

The London Naval Conference of 1930 sought to restrict the naval prowess of the major naval forces in the world. Following the destruction of World War I, the meetings were held with the aim of advancing disarmament. The Washington Conference of 1921-22 marked the start of them, while the London Conference of 1935 marked their conclusion. Great Britain, the United States, Japan, France, and Italy convened a new conference in London in 1930 following a failed Geneva meeting in 1927. attempts to amend and broaden the terms of the Five Powers Treaty of 1922. By 1930, both sides were eager to reach an agreement to avoid a full-scale arms race and, more importantly, to force their naval officers to sit behind their diplomats during negotiations. Another significant issue at the 1930s convention was the maximum ton for light cruisers. The United States resisted a limit of less than 10,000 tons due to the nature of its international commitments, especially its involvement in the Philippines and East Asia, and the limited supply of refueling station-light cruisers in the Pacific. These levels were not changed by the London treaty, but definition of an aircraft carrier was amended to include vessels under 10,000 tons used for this purpose and it was stipulated that such vessels must not be armed with greater than six inch guns (Kisner, JR., 1941, P. 39). While other nations were far more ready to accept the British maximum of 7,000 tons, the United States refused to concede on this subject, despite the fact that it jeopardized Japanese proportions and heavy cruisers. Ultimately, the American stance won out. Nevertheless, the second conflict resulted dehumanization from these accords' failure. The Washington and Geneva Conferences failed to put any limitations on auxiliary vessels, while the London Conference was slightly more successful than its predecessors in this

area. To control these categories, the United States, Japan, and Great Britain established a three-power agreement. This agreement established the maximum tonnage levels that may be achieved by 1936 in the cruiser, destroyer, and submarine classes. The following were the levels of Naval powers:

Category	United States	Great Britain	Japan
Cruisers	180,000	146,000	108,400
	145,500	192,200	
Destroyers	150,000	150,000	105,000
Submarines	52,700	52,000	52,000

Source: H. Kisner, JR. (1941). The London Naval Conference of 1930. Oklahoma Agricultural and Mechanical College Library, pp. 39.

The world's leading nations were highly enthused by the work done at the London Conference in 1930, but this optimism was short-lived. The residual mistrust and animosities from the World War prevented any kind of humanitarian understanding between nations. This resulted from the uneasy sense of approaching danger and the ongoing fear of attack. The world was headed toward war as a result of these responses.

Sanction Against Italy (The most notable part of dehumanization):

Following the conclusion of the Stresa Conference, Italy made an effort to broaden its influence. Benito Mussolini, the dictator of Italy, was able to extend his dominion into Africa because to the Anglo-German Naval Agreement. In this case, the League of Nations declared Italy to be an aggressive state and urged everyone to oppose it. Italy invaded one region after another and persisted in its invasions without facing any consequences. The British view was that the character of the Ethiopian Government and the conditions prevailing in that wild land of tyranny, slavery, and tribal war were not consonant with membership of the League. But the Italians had had their way, and Abyssinia was a member of the League, with all its rights and such securities as it could offer (Churchill, 1948, P. 149). Then Ethiopia, Eritrea and Somalia were captured and the three countries united to form a colony called Italian East Africa. Then, on June 30, 1936, Emperor Haile Selassie addressed the League of Nations and vehemently denounced Italy's conduct. It sparked a catastrophic war over the world.

The period of the sanctions against Italy was limited to November 1935-June 1936. They consisted of: 'The first Proposal, which prohibited the trade of weapons to Ethiopia and Italy. The second proposal, which "asked States to render impossible all loans to or for the Italian Government, or banking or other credits to or for that Government or any public authority, person, or corporation in Italian territory, and all issues of shares or other capital flotations in Italian

territory or elsewhere, made directly or indirectly for the Italian Government or for public authorities, persons, or corporations established in Italian territory," had been included. The third proposal "related to the prohibition of importation into the territory of State Members of all consigned from Italy or Italian possessions". The fourth Proposal, which "prohibited the exportation or re-exportation to Italy and her colonies of a certain number of articles which were necessary for the prosecution of war and mainly exported by States Members of the League" (Ristuccia, 1997, P. 5). In essence, the majority of sanctions were ineffective. The Department of State asked American firms to comply with oil sanctions imposed by the League of Nations on Italy in 1936 due to its war against Abyssinia, but it was unable to compel them to do so. The larger companies stopped delivering oil to Italy since their operations were well known. Consequently, the oil prices in Italy and Italian Somaliland surged, which made the business attractive. By buying gasoline, renting tankers, and transporting it to the Italian soldiers, several small enterprises made substantial profits.

Rise of Hitler And Establishment of Dictatorship:

One important event following World War I was the fall of the German monarchy. The monarchy was abolished and the nation was proclaimed a republic in 1919, led by Erbert, the head of the Social Democratic Party. A two-chamber parliament and an adult vote would elect the president for a seven-year term, according to the constitution drafted by German delegates at Weimar. The "Weimar Republic" is the historical name for it. However, this 'Weimar Republic' was unable to endure primarily because of the conflict between the far right and the far left, instability, the refusal of affluent industrialists to cooperate, economic catastrophe, foreign policy failure, etc. In the 1933 elections to the lower house of the German parliament, the National Socialist Party (Nazi Party) won 288 of the 647 seats. But when the law and order situation deteriorated, the then President Hindenburg appointed Hitler as chancellor instead of Von Papen (1933). After Hindenburg's death in 1934, Hitler declared himself president of the Republic. He was thus appointed president and chancellor at the same time. Hitler came to power and took the initiative to complete the unification of Germany and Austria. Hitler backed Franco during the Civil War in Spain at the time. Japan and Germany signed an anti-Communist treaty in 1936. Germany, Japan, and Italy signed the Rome-Berlin Tokyo Axis accord in 1937 after Italy joined the treaty. It was a treaty against Britain, France and Russia. Hitler followed dehumanizing policy in the most of the time. By signing a pact with Czechoslovakia, he ended the state's existence there. He took the port of Memel from Lithuania by force. He also took control of Poland's Danzig port at the same time. He so launched World War II by invading Poland on September 1, 1939. From 1939 until 1945, the conflict lasted six years.

Economic Nationalism:

In response to the Great Depression of 1929, other European states, including the United States, adopted more or less isolated and self-sufficient economies. This situation is called "Economic Nationalism". Economic nationalism means "Autarky" in German. The etymological meaning of the word "Autarky" is

'economic self-sufficiency'. The term *autarky* means to achieve commercial self-sufficiency within the internal boundaries of the national state.

In the late 1930s, economic nationalism took a perverse aggressive form as a result of dehumanization, the Great Depression and the crisis of the exchange system. Firstly, European nations that had long struggled with unemployment sought to halt foreign trade and increase employment through artificial means. Secondly, Germany and other countries were involved in large amounts of domestic and foreign debt. However, there was no fixed deposit behind this loan. Thirdly, in Italy and Germany, the arms industry was organized to quickly solve the unemployment problem. Naturally, these two countries tend to gravitate towards aggressive foreign policy. In this case, it should be remembered that not every country has resorted to aggressive foreign policy under the influence of economic nationalism. Such influence ultimately led to a devastating war for the planet.

The Beginning and Dynamics of WWII from the effects of Dehumanization

The World War II began with Hitler's invasion of Poland on September 1, 1939. Even in World War II, the world's most powerful states were divided into two parts. In 1939 Germany clearly saw war precisely as an instrument of national policy (Inoma-Abbey, Akpenyi & Igwe, 2021, P. 168). The axis's main adversary was the Allies made up of Britain, France and the United States. Russia was also on the team. When Hitler invaded the Soviet Union in June 1941, the Allies were considering opening a second battlefield anywhere in Western Europe. But two years later, no decision has been taken in this regard, though J. Stalin has repeatedly requested the same. There is disagreement as to the reason for this delay. There were differing opinions on where the second battlefield would be opened. Winston Churchill supported entering Germany via the Balkans or Italy. In essence, however, the American generals supported the transoceanic landing of troops in Western Europe, notwithstanding the challenges involved. An Allied landing was a possibility that Germany had anticipated. Four years of German occupation of the seashore led to the impenetrable Atlantic area. Nevertheless, in addition to Marshal Rundstedt, Hitler appointed Field Marshal Rommel to this special duty in order to increase the resistance. Regarding the plan, however, the two disagreed. In the air, sea, and land domains, the Allied side outperformed the Germans. On the eastern barrier, the Red Army divided into five fronts and rapidly moved towards the German border while the Allies were fighting the Berlin campaign on the western frontier. Hitler erected a number of barriers at the city's entry to safeguard the German capital.

On April 18, the Russian army crossed the Spree River and on April 20 attacked the German army headquarters in Josen. On April 21, Russian forces entered Berlin and street fighting broke out. Germany and Italy surrendered to the Allies in April 1945 in the wake of a series of German defeats in the war. Mussolini was detained and assassinated, while Hitler, unable to accept defeat, committed himself on April 30, 1945. However, at the 'Potasdam Conference' on August 2, 1945, the United States, Britain, and Russia requested that Japan surrender; Japan

declined. Atomic bombs were later dropped on Hiroshima and Nagasaki on August 6 and 9. The Hiroshima and Nagasaki incidents were the most terrible symbol of dehumanization in the world. One thing is good to say here, and that is the attack on Pearl Harbor by Japan. Japan attacked the U.S. Naval and Air Base at Pearl Harbor on the Hawaiian island of Wahoo on December 7, 1941. The Americans decided to hit Japan with a missile. They planned to build an atomic bomb. On July 16, 1945, the United States successfully detonated an atomic bomb in the desert of New Mexico. Just three weeks later, atomic bombs were carried out on Hiroshima (August 6) and Nagasaki (August 9). As a result, Japan surrendered unconditionally on August 14 (1945). Thus, the Allies won WWII. In this war many of the principles of the laws of war were violated, especially by the bombing of cities, the ruthless treatment of many prisoners of war and the appalling treatment of Jews, Gypsies, and others in many of the Axis occupied territories. Leading Axis leaders were targeted for punishment by the International Military Tribunals which were held at Tokyo and Nuremberg just after the war as well as by numerous other tribunals. Despite being significantly less horrible than those of the Axis countries, Allied military tactics were mainly ignored.

Establishment of the United Nations

Although the League of Nations failed, the founders of the United Nations were inspired by the idea of the League of Nations. The name "United Nations" was first coined by U.S. President Franklin D. Roosevelt on January 1, 1945. During World War II, with representatives from 26 countries declaring war against the Axis powers by combined force for the first time. At the "Conference of Nations" on international organization in San Francisco which took place from April 25 to June 26, 1945, representatives of 50 nations drafted the United Nations Charter. At the Dumbarton Oaks meeting in Washington in August and October of 1944, officials from China, France, the Soviet Union, the United Kingdom, and the United States made ideas that were the basis for the Charter. The 50 states' representatives participating in the conference ratified and signed the charter on June 26, 1945. Poland became one of the first 51 signatories to the agreement despite not attending the summit. With the approval of the charter by China, France, the Soviet Union, the United Kingdom, the United States, and the majority of the other signatories, the United Nations was formally created on October 24, 1945.

Evaluation

Peace, security, and democracy were threatened by dehumanized activities of the nations during the two wars. It is clear that democracy, security and peace were not safe at that moments. That's why the period between the two great wars is called the long ceasefire rather than a peaceful time. Everyone dehumanized each other and was interested in preserving their own democracy, peace and security. And this interest ultimately made war inevitable. Germany believed that there was no such thing as security in the face of the great power, while France and Great Britain believed that democracy and peace were in peril. Hitler thought that all other races were inferior and that Germans were the sole superior race in

the world. Therefore, it makes perfect sense for the best to rule over the worst. Hitler was obsessed with the dream that the Germans would dominate the whole of Europe. He risked an all-out war to make his dream a reality. Both Mussolini and Hitler saw democracy as a problem and agreed that the best way to annihilate it was through totalitarianism. They believed that it was not possible to solve economic problems through democratic means, there was no option but totalitarianism for the rapid development of the country. Hitler and Mussolini, swayed by militant nationalism, sought to dominate the whole of Europe. Their motives were followed by dehumanization policy. On the eve of World War II, human civilization, world peace and internationalism had become worthless. The World War II witnessed the horrors of the atomic bomb which is the most terrible indication of dehumanization. The 20th century witnessed the rise of several (eight) countries that declared themselves nuclear powers. The fact that society focused on the arms race in spite of the atrocities of World War II was a huge failure. And if we look at it, it can be seen that today's world and different countries are moving forward with their authoritarian attitude. The big powers are always suppressing the weak forces with dehumanization policy.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this research demonstrates that the First World War was not merely a historical conflict of territorial and political disputes but a profound catalyst for the systematic dehumanization of individuals and societies. Extreme nationalism, intense economic and military competition, and conflicting alliances all fueled a climate where human dignity was continuously eroded. The harrowing conditions of trench warfare, the introduction of poison gas, and the mass mobilization of people as expendable tools of war revealed the depths of inhumanity that industrialized warfare could reach. The armistice that followed did not restore human dignity or secure lasting peace. Instead, punitive measures like the Treaty of Versailles, the failure of the League of Nations, and unresolved imperial ambitions created fertile ground for further dehumanizing ideologies to flourish-most notoriously fascism and totalitarianism. Events such as the Italo-Abyssinian War, the Spanish Civil War, and the Japanese naval arms race illustrate how unresolved tensions and power struggles perpetuated cycles of violence and human degradation. The literature shows that thinkers, historians, and authors alike have scrutinized these wars to understand how entire societies could justify mass atrocities by systematically stripping away the humanity of others. This historical pattern warns that without vigilant commitment to peace, justice, and respect for human life, technological and ideological advancements will continue to threaten humanity itself. Therefore, the First and Second World Wars, though distinct in chronology, are inseparably linked through a continuous thread of dehumanization- a tragic testament to how war, driven by human ambitions and fears, can unravel the very fabric of what it means to be human.

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